

INFLUENCE OF SPAN RATIO ON THE FOUR-POINT BEND END NOTCHED FLEXURE TEST

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ABSTRACT

Delamination is one of the primary failure modes for laminated composite structures. Extensive investigations have been made on experimental characterization of interlaminar fracture toughness. Standard test methods are currently available for mode I and mixed mode I+II delamination, and three-point bend End Notched Flexure (3ENF) has recently been standardized as ASTM D7905. However, the interlaminar crack propagation in 3ENF test is conditionally stable and yields only the initiation value of mode II interlaminar fracture toughness, which prevent the measurement of mode II R-curve. Four-point bend End Notched Flexure (4ENF) is another choice in determination of mode II fracture toughness since crack propagation is more stable under displacement controlled load than that of 3ENF. In the present work, the influence of inner to outer span ratio of 4ENF test specimen is experimentally investigated. Span ratios of 40%, 50% and 60% are obtained by varying the inner span while keeping outer span constant. 3ENF test is performed on the same batch of material for comparison. Compliance calibration approach is utilized to establish relationship between crack length and compliance of the specimen, which is further used to evaluate the fracture toughness G_{IIC} during fracture tests. The effects of crack initiation from both the Teflon insert end and natural crack front are discussed and compared. It is found that more conservative results are given from natural crack in all test configurations. Experiment results show that span ratio has little influence on the toughness values in the 4ENF tests. The toughness obtained by 3ENF test is 13% to 19% lower than those of 4ENF.

1 INTRODUCTION

The increasing application of fiber-reinforced composite laminates have attracted much attention of industrial manufacturers, engineers and researchers. Despite its high intralaminar strength and stiffness, the laminate exhibits a low resistance to interlaminar damage. The interlaminar damage, also called delamination, is one of the common failure modes in composite laminates, which can interact with intralaminar cracks and may cause significant loss of structural stiffness and strength. Therefore, it is important to establish accurate characterization methods for the evaluation of interlaminar fracture resistance. The double cantilever beam (DCB)[1-2] and mixed-mode bending (MMB)[3-4] test methods have been standardized by international standard associations (e.g. ASTM) and are widely used to determine the interlaminar fracture toughness in the cases of pure mode I and mixed mode I/II, respectively.

After many years of research, several test methods have been proposed to determine the mode II fracture resistance, such as the three-point end notched flexure (3ENF) [5-6], four-point end notched flexure (4ENF) [7-8], end loaded split (ELS) [9] and center notched flexure (CNF) [10]. Recently, 3ENF has been standardized as ASTM D7905 [5] standard test method. However, the interlaminar crack propagation in 3ENF test is conditionally stable and yields only the initiation value of mode II interlaminar fracture toughness, which prevent the measurement of mode II R-curve. To overcome the disadvantage of 3ENF, Martin and Davidson [11] has proposed a simple 4ENF test method, which has the feature of stable crack propagation and is able to evaluate the initiation and propagation toughness G_{IIC} . Experimental studies [7, 11] showed that the G_{IIC} from 4ENF may be 9-60% higher than those from 3ENF test. It is also reported that the toughness value increases with the increasing ratio of inner to outer span length in 4ENF test [12]. Nevertheless, available experiment results are still inadequate to support the above conclusions. In the present work, 4ENF tests are performed to investigate the

influence of inner to outer span ratio on the measurement of mode II fracture toughness. The effects of crack initiation from both Teflon insert and natural cracks are discussed and compared. 3ENF test are carried out as well to verify the inconsistency between two test methods.

2. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

2.1 Specimen and experimental procedure

All specimens for 4ENF and 3ENF tests were made from CCF300/BA9916-II carbon/epoxy composite and were cut from the same 24 ply unidirectional plate. All specimens are 180mm long, 20mm wide and nearly 3mm thick, with a nominal ply thickness of 0.125mm. A Teflon film insert was implanted at one end of each specimen and located in the mid-plane of the plate to serve as a crack starter. The nominal full length of the Teflon insert is 70mm for each specimen. The material properties provided by the manufacturer are given in Table.1.

E_{11}	E_{22}	ν_{12}	G_{12}
137 GPa	9.7 GPa	0.31	6.0 GPa

Table.1 Material properties of CCF300/BA9916-II carbon/epoxy composite

Referring to Fig.1a, a series of 4ENF tests under three inner to outer span ratios ($d/2L=40\%$, 50% , 60%) were performed to investigate the influence of span ratio on the measurement of mode II interlaminar fracture toughness. The span ratios were implemented by keeping the outer span length $2L$ constant ($2L=120\text{mm}$) and varying the inner span length d ($d=48, 60, 72\text{mm}$, respectively). There are four specimens in each configuration. The lateral faces of each specimen edge were coated with white paint in order to make markings for compliance calibration (CC) and help observing the delamination crack front.

Fig.1b shows the photograph of the 4ENF fixture used in this study. The loading platen on the top can rotate about the specimen's width direction to produce equal forces at two loading pins. To allow for the specimen sliding among different parts with minimal friction during bending, the support pins on the base and loading pins on the loading platen were equipped with roller bearings. A constraint is placed at uncracked end of the specimen to keep it from sliding in longitudinal direction since the corresponding force component is non-zero. Two linear variable displacement transducers (LVDT) are positioned at two end side of the loading platen and made contact with its top surface to record the displacement at that two points, so that the displacements at the loading pins can be derived. The tests were carried out on an Instron 8872 machine with a 5kN load cell. During the test, load and deflection values were continuously recorded where the deflection was taken to be the LVDT displacement.

Fig.1 4ENF test: (a) specimen geometry configuration (b) photograph of the fixture

The compliance calibration approach is performed for each specimen to establish relationship between interlaminar crack length and specimen compliance, which is further used to evaluate the fracture toughness G_{IIC} during fracture tests. Non-precracked (NPC) and precracked (PC) fracture toughnesses were both determined from the same specimen. The crack advance from Teflon insert during NPC fracture test creates the natural crack that is then used for PC test. The complete test

procedures are given in Fig.2. A two-point NPC compliance calibration test is firstly conducted, and the NPC fracture test is followed to form the natural crack front. After that, a four-point PC compliance calibration test is performed followed by the PC fracture test. Finally, the specimen is fully pried open along its middle plane to measure the actual length of Teflon insert.

Fig.2 Test procedures

For a given inner to outer span ratio configuration, the specimen was placed in the fixture in such a position that the nominal effective insert length equals a_1 , which is the length between nominal end position of the insert and the right support roller. Compliance calibration test was performed by loading the specimen up to the peak CC force, which is half the critical force estimated using beam theory [11], and then unloading. The force and deflection data (LVDT displacement) were continuously recorded and corresponding loading compliance C_1 was obtained. Next, the specimen was shifted to the second position where the nominal effective insert length was a_2 , and the specimen was reloaded to determine the compliance C_2 . After the NPC calibration test, the specimen was shifted to the third position with a nominal effective insert length of a_3 . The specimen was loaded until the crack extended about 20mm and then unloaded. The critical load, compliance before crack extension C_3^{load} and the unloading compliance after crack extension C_3^{unload} can be obtained in the NPC fracture test. In this study, the relationship among these nominal effective insert lengths are $a_1 < a_3 < a_2$. The exact effective insert lengths were modified by the actual full length of Teflon insert that was measured after the PC fracture test.

	span ratio 40%	span ratio 50%	span ratio 60%	test
a_1	60 mm	60 mm	60 mm	NPC CC
a_2	45 mm	40 mm	40 mm	NPC CC
a_3	50 mm	50 mm	50 mm	NPC fracture
a_4	80 mm	80 mm	80 mm	PC CC
a_5	70 mm	70 mm	70 mm	PC CC
a_6	60 mm	60 mm	60 mm	PC CC
a_7	45 mm	40 mm	40 mm	PC CC
a_8	50 mm	50 mm	50 mm	PC fracture

Table.2 The nominal effective crack/insert length used in the 4ENF tests

The NPC fracture test creates the natural crack that is used in PC calibration and PC fracture tests. The specimen was repositioned to the fourth location with the nominal effective crack length equaled a_4 , which is the length between nominal crack tip position, obtained by assuming that the full length of the insert is 70mm and the crack advance is exactly 20mm, and the right support roller. Compliance calibration test was conducted again to determine the compliance C_4 . The PC calibration tests were subsequently carried out for another three nominal effective crack lengths a_5 , a_6 and a_7 . Afterwards, the specimen was shifted to the position with a nominal effective crack length equaled a_8 and loaded until crack advance occurred. The actual effective crack lengths a_i ($i=4, 5, \dots, 8$) were modified by

using the a - C curve established from NPC tests. The nominal effective crack/insert length used in the 4ENF tests for different span ratio configurations are given in Table.2.

The 3ENF tests were conducted according to ASTM D7905 standard method. As shown in Fig.3, the fixture span length is $2L=100\text{mm}$, and the nominal effective insert/crack length is 35mm in NPC fracture test and 25mm in PC fracture test, which were all modified in the same way as in 4ENF test.

Fig.3 3ENF test: (a) specimen geometry configuration (b) photograph of the fixture

2.2 Data reduction

The fracture toughness G_{IIC} is the energy needed for advancing a crack of length a to $a+\Delta a$ at the critical load P_C and critical displacement δ_C :

$$G_{IIC} = \frac{P_C^2}{2B} \frac{\partial C}{\partial a} \quad (1)$$

where B is specimen width and $C = \delta / P$ is specimen compliance. The critical load P_C is the maximum value of force on the load-deflection curve. The specimen's deflection δ in 4ENF test is the average of the displacements at two loading pins which are derived from LVDT readings:

$$\delta = \frac{w_L + w_R}{2} \quad (2)$$

where w_L and w_R represent the displacements at left and right loading pins, respectively.

The relationships between crack length and compliance are usually expressed linearly as:

$$C_{4ENF} = A + ma \quad (3)$$

$$C_{3ENF} = A + ma^3 \quad (4)$$

where A is the intercept and m is the slope, which are the constants obtained from the linear regression analysis of experimental data. It should be noted that the constants A and m are determined in NPC and PC tests separately even for the same specimen.

By substituting Eq.(3) and Eq.(4) into Eq.(1), the fracture toughnesses G_{IIC} of NPC and PC tests can be determined for 4ENF and 3ENF configurations respectively:

$$G_{IIC}^{4ENF} = \frac{mP_C^2}{2B} \quad (5)$$

$$G_{IIC}^{3ENF} = \frac{3ma^2P_C^2}{2B} \quad (6)$$

Since the crack did not always grow to a length of exact 20mm during the NPC fracture test, the actual crack length is estimated after NPC fracture test by substituting unloading compliance, C_{4ENF}^{unload} or C_{3ENF}^{unload} , into Eq.(3) or Eq.(4), which yields:

$$a = \frac{C_{4ENF}^{\text{unload}} - A}{m} \quad \text{for 4ENF test} \quad (7)$$

$$a = \sqrt[3]{\frac{C_{3ENF}^{unload} - A}{m}} \quad \text{for 3ENF test} \quad (8)$$

The estimated actual crack length is then used to correct the nominal crack length in PC tests.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.4 presents the typical plots of crack length vs. compliance for 3ENF and 4ENF tests, where each set of data points has been fit to a straight line. Small deviations from the linear lines are observed in two cases of both configurations. Fig.4a shows the typical a - C curve for 4ENF test with different span ratios. It can be seen that the linear compliance line in PC test is obviously lower than that in NPC test, but those for 3ENF are almost coincide with each other, which may be due to the different sensitivity of both configurations to the existing fracture process zone ahead of natural crack tip.

Fig.4 Typical plots of crack length versus compliance for: (a) 4ENF test (b) 3ENF test

Fig.5 Experimental fracture toughness from NPC and PC tests in 4ENF and 3ENF configurations

The experimental mode II fracture toughness G_{IIC} from NPC and PC tests of both configurations are given in Fig.5. The most apparent observation is that in all cases the G_{IIC} from NPC tests are higher than that from PC tests, to the amount of 7.5% to 19% for 4ENF and 35% for 3ENF. This can be attributed to the existence of resin rich region in front of insert's end from which the crack initiates in NPC test and causes an artificial increases of G_{IIC} . Therefore, the toughness from PC test is considered to be the true value since it represents the actual fracture states in usual laminate. The values of G_{IIC} from 4ENF PC tests under the span ratios of 40%, 50% and 60% are 1.51, 1.59 and 1.57 kJ/m², respectively. The difference of toughness values among the three span ratios is within 5.2%. Considering the large scatter of the results in the same span ratio (the c.v. may be up to 10%), we conclude that the inner to outer span ratio in the 4ENF test has little influence on the toughness value. This conclusion is different from Martin et al. [12] and Davidson et al. [8], who observed an increase

or decrease of toughness with increasing span ratio. According to our experience, a span ratio no less than 50% is recommended since larger inner span length leaves more space for crack extension to establish detailed R-curve.

Meanwhile, it is interesting to note that the scatter in toughness data is significantly less for 3ENF than it is for 4ENF test. The values as obtained by 3ENF test is 1.34 kJ/m^2 , which is 13% to 19% lower than those of 4ENF. This finding is similar to that presented by Martin and Davidson [11]. Generally, the difference between 3ENF and 4ENF tests is considered arising from friction, shear deformation or geometrical nonlinearity. However, Davidson et al. [8] thought that fixture compliance plays a large role and the 4ENF test produces structural quantities rather than material properties. Further investigation is needed to clarify this issue.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The influence of inner to outer span ratio on four-point bend End Notched Flexure (4ENF) was experimentally investigated by keeping outer span constant while varying inner span length to get three span ratios of 40%, 50% and 60%. Three-point bend End Notched Flexure (3ENF) was also performed to present the inconsistency between two test methods. Compliance calibration approach was utilized to establish the relationship between crack length and compliance, which was further used to evaluate the fracture toughness G_{IIC} during fracture tests. The effects of crack initiation from either Teflon insert or natural cracks were discussed and compared. It was found that natural crack yields more conservative results of fracture toughness in two configurations and all test cases and should be considered as the true value. The experimental results show that span ratio in 4ENF test has little influence on the toughness values. The toughness obtained by 3ENF test is 13% to 19% lower than those of 4ENF.

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